

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Report

Sample Name **NS128**
Comment

Instrument maXis 4G
Method ms_nocolumn_mid_pos.m

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Measured m/z vs. theoretical m/z

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	z
935.4646	1	C 56 H 64 Co N 10	100.00	935.4642	-0.5	-0.5	124.1	30.0	odd	1+

Mass list

#	m/z	I %	I
1	149.9525	1.2	8718
2	201.1094	6.6	49492
3	205.0596	5.2	39100
4	214.9170	1.4	10501
5	217.1043	1.4	10951
6	220.9342	1.5	11314
7	224.9928	2.4	18001
8	226.9512	11.3	85693
9	229.0499	1.9	14509
10	238.8837	1.8	13563
11	239.0886	3.2	24422
12	239.1612	1.4	10216
13	242.9250	1.4	10702
14	245.0782	1.2	9163
15	250.9919	2.2	16794
16	251.0525	1.4	10846
17	255.1563	1.6	12231
18	257.0629	1.4	10673
19	257.1507	1.2	9100
20	261.1303	1.3	9706
21	281.0479	1.9	14689
22	288.9216	8.2	62060
23	290.9248	2.6	19277
24	294.9194	2.4	18463
25	296.2191	2.5	19002
26	301.1405	1.9	14512
27	312.8880	1.9	14032
28	317.2444	2.4	17906
29	319.2600	3.2	24045
30	335.1669	1.3	9549
31	350.8919	1.3	9800
32	353.2655	3.5	26109
33	356.9086	1.5	11335
34	360.3230	3.3	24980
35	362.9258	2.8	21457
36	365.1056	1.3	9832
37	379.1931	2.1	15795
38	381.1004	1.5	11561
39	381.2967	2.5	19208
40	393.2967	1.2	9052
41	413.2653	1.5	11235
42	418.8790	1.2	9001
43	423.2194	3.2	24522
44	424.8960	4.1	30840
45	430.9130	2.9	21554
46	439.1245	1.8	13260
47	441.2966	5.2	38914
48	442.2997	1.4	10769
49	443.3333	1.5	11049
50	448.8625	2.4	18439
51	450.8599	1.6	11914
52	452.8585	1.2	8764
53	467.1012	7.9	59579
54	467.2453	4.0	29950
55	467.7311	2.7	20678
56	468.1018	3.5	26162
57	468.2334	1.8	13307
58	469.0993	2.2	16878
59	484.2298	2.0	14742
60	484.7314	1.3	9516
61	486.8666	1.7	12784
62	487.3595	1.4	10952

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#	m/z	I %	I
63	492.8834	2.2	16659
64	497.3955	1.9	14030
65	498.8999	1.3	9729
66	511.2714	3.9	29682
67	513.1427	3.5	26393
68	513.3697	1.4	10569
69	514.1432	1.5	11165
70	531.3855	1.4	10518
71	536.1641	3.2	24014
72	537.1650	1.5	11248
73	541.1198	7.8	58613
74	542.1203	3.7	28009
75	543.1179	2.5	19192
76	553.3883	2.1	15650
77	553.4580	5.7	43376
78	554.4612	2.3	17297
79	554.8536	1.3	9695
80	555.2975	3.4	25868
81	557.0933	1.5	11292
82	560.8705	2.0	14776
83	566.8875	1.5	11320
84	569.4319	5.1	38271
85	570.4351	1.8	13927
86	575.4114	1.2	9223
87	599.3238	2.4	18456
88	622.8406	1.3	9690
89	628.8575	1.7	12783
90	643.3493	1.5	11412
91	685.4340	2.2	16515
92	690.8281	1.2	8714
93	696.8452	1.6	12344
94	764.8320	1.2	8889
95	935.4646	100.0	755563
96	935.9564	1.3	10003
97	936.2413	2.2	16362
98	936.4677	80.5	608061
99	937.4705	43.4	328031
100	938.4727	8.3	62556

Acquisition Parameter

General	Fore Vacuum	2.39e+000 mBar	High Vacuum	9.56e-008 mBar	Source Type	ESI
	Scan Begin	75 m/z	Scan End	2000 m/z	Ion Polarity	Positive
Source	Set Nebulizer	2.0 Bar	Set Capillary	4500 V	Set Dry Gas	8.0 l/min
	Set Dry Heater	200 °C	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V		
Quadrupole	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV				
Coll. Cell	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Collision Cell RF	600.0 Vpp	100.0 Vpp	
Ion Cooler	Set Ion Cooler Transfer Time	75.0 µs	Set Ion Cooler Pre Pulse Storage Time	10.0 µs		